

PREDICTION FOR TENTH BHAVA AND PLANETS

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Abstract:

Uthyogam Purushalakshanam is the proverb in Tamil. A man is given respected by his job or profession only. So, it plays a vital role in our life. We can choose our apt profession or job according to our horoscope.

Key Words: 10th bhava, Sun, Moon, Mars, Mercury, Jupiter, Venus, Saturn Rahu, Kethu, Sun and Moon, Sun and Mars, Sun and Mercury, Sun and Jupiter, Sun and Venus, Sun and Saturn, Moon and Mars, Moon and Mercury, Moon and Saturn, Mars and Jupiter, Mars and Venus, Mars and Saturn, Mercury and Venus, Jupiter and Venus, Jupiter and Saturn, Best direction for profession, home town or out of town, which best for profession.

Introduction:

In this world money is the main need to live happily. One can earn money through doing a profession. So, profession is very important vs. If we select the right profession we will win the world.

Who Helps us Our Profession?

- Sun in 10th bhava: Father, Politician, elders in family, Ministers and higher government officials will help to improve our profession.
- Moon in 10th bhava: Mother, Mother in Law, and powerful ladies will help to improve our profession.
- Mars in 10th bhava: Younger brothers, Police, Army man will help to improve our profession.
- Mercury in 10th bhava: Friends, relatives, maternal uncle, astrologers, auditors, commission agents will help to improve our profession.
- Jupiter in 10th bhava: Teachers, Priests, Saints will help to improve our profession.
- Venus in 10th bhava: Wife, aunt and beautiful young ladies will help to improve our profession.
- Saturn in 10th bhava: Differently abled persons, physical labours and elder brothers will help to improve our profession.
- Rahu in 10 bhava: Muslims will help to improve our profession.
- Kethu in 10 bhava: Christians will help to improve our profession.

Planets Conjunctions in 10th Bhava:

- Sun with Moon in 10th bhava: The native will get the best position in government. He will easily pass in departmental examination for promotion. He will be sincere in his duty. He will be a minister.
- Sun with Mars in 10th bhava: The native has influence in higher officials. He / She will Shine in the field of medical department and also in police and military. He / She will be a minister and the governor.
- Sun with Mercury in 10th bhava: The native will be an I.A.S Officer. Transport and News department give him / her name and fame.
- Sun with Jupiter in 10th bhava: The native will shine in finance department and endowment department. Surely he/she will reach the highest position gradually.
- Sun with Venus in 10th bhava: The native will shine in research related government jobs He / She will shine each and every department.
- Sun with Saturn in 10th bhava: The native will go to abroad. Government related professions give a lot of suffer. Private sector gives peace of mind.
- Moon with Mars in 10th bhava: The native will shine in agriculture, transport and estate related professions.
- Moon with Mercury in 10th bhava: The native will shine in secretary post and minister. Both government and private sectors he/she will shine.
- Moon with Jupiter in 10th bhava: The native will shine in politics and teaching profession. Agriculture department is also favours.
- Moon with Venus in 10th bhava: The native will shine as an ambassador or the governor. Food and marine transport give name and fame to him/her.
- Moon with Saturn in 10th bhava: The native will shine in gold jewellery business. Marine transport gives name and fame to him / her.

- Mars with Mercury in 10th bhava: The native will shine in multimedia, communications, press, phone and telegram, sectors.
- Mars with Jupiter in 10th bhava: The native will shine as the village administrative officer. Gradually he/she will reach the District collector post. He/She will work as the president in their association.
- Mars with Venus in 10th bhava: The native will shine as the minister, collector, governor expert in surgery and military.
- Mars with Saturn in 10th bhava: The native will shine as a bill collector, ameena, surveyor, constable in prison and also a home guard.
- Mercury with Jupiter in 10th bhava: The native will shine as the officer in school, college, legislative assembly, municipality and corporation.
- Mercury with Venus in 10th bhava: The native will shine in commercial department and cinema. He / she will do prostitution business very well.
- Jupiter with Venus in 10th bhava: The native will shine as the minister, judge, collector, governor etc. He /She works in the honourable post.
- Jupiter with Saturn in 10th bhava: The native will shine in high level government jobs very well. Commercial department will be favour to him / her.
- Venus with Saturn in 10th bhava: The native will shine in labour department, research and transport department.

Best Direction for Profession:

There are two options to choose the best direction for profession.

- According to tenth bhava: One should choose the best direction for profession according to his/her tenth bhava. Each rasi has a particular direction

S.No	10th Sign	Best direction for Profession
1	Aries	East
2	Taurus	South
3	Gemini	West
4	Cancer	North
5	Leo	East
6	Virgo	South
7	Libra	West
8	Scorpio	North
9	Sagittarius	East
10	Capricorn	South
11	Aquaris	West
12	Pisces	North

- According to 10th Lord: One should choose the best direction for profession according to his tenth Lord. Every planet has the particular direction

S.No	10th Lord	Best direction for Profession
1	Sun	All directions
2	Moon	South east
3	Mars	South
4	Mercury	North east
5	Jupiter	North
6	Venus	East
7	Saturn	West
8	Rahu (shadow planet)	South west
9	Kethu (shadow planet)	North west

If Rahu or kethu stands in tenth bhava, we consider it as the tenth Lord.

Which place? is best for profession? Home town or out of home town?

There are three rules for the above question.

- Rule 1: If the tenth house of the native should be Aries / Cancer / Libra / Capricorn and also the tenth Lord stands in Aries / Cancer / Libra / Capricorn he/she will do his profession in out of home town is the very best one.
- Rule 2: If the tenth house of the native should be and also the tenth Lord stands in Taurus/ Leo / Scorpio / Aquaris he/she will do his profession in home town is the very best one.
- Rule 3: If the tenth house of the native should be and also the tenth Lord stands in Gemini / Virgo / Sagittarius / Pisces he/she will often change his town.

Conclusion:

One will do his business or job according to his tenth Lord and its standing navamsa bhava Lord. It gives huge success. The above 20 combinations will be very useful for the universe.

References:

1. www.astro.com
2. Jeevana bhavam written by C.G. Rajan published by Giri Trading Agency, Chennai.
3. Palatheebigai published by Sri Anantha Nilaiyam, Chennai
4. BrihatSamhitha written by Dr.K.N.Saraswathi published by Kadalangudi Publications.
5. Jothida Peragarathi M.N.Rajan published by Sagunthala Nilaiyam, Chennai.
6. Nakshatra chintamani written by Pulippani Sundaravaradhachariyar published by Saraswathi Mahal library, Tanjore.